

HYGROTHERMAL AGEING AND CREEP BEHAVIOR OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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Abstract

In the present paper, pultruded GFRP pipes were immersed in water at 20°C, 40°C and 60°C for six months. The water absorption and diffusion, flexural properties and short beam shear strength were investigated. It was found that the saturation water content and the coefficient of diffusion are negligibly affected by the immersion temperatures. This is because the diffusion of the water in the present GFRP composites may be mainly occurred along the interfaces between the fiber and resin matrix, rather than through the resin matrix. This is also confirmed by the activation energy of the diffusion, which is only 8 kJ/mol, much lower than those of polymer resins or polymer based composites.

Water immersion leads to the degradation of the flexural properties due to the damage of the interfaces. Meanwhile, the flexural strength is more sensitive to the water immersion than the modulus. The short beam shear strength is reduced by the water immersion dramatically, which is correlated to the water uptake content. The higher the water uptake content, the more reduced the short beam shear strength.

1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites have been widely used for construction applications due to its excellent properties (e.g., light weight, high corrosion resistance) compared to traditional civil engineering materials, such as steel and concrete, and relatively cost effective compared to carbon fiber reinforced FRPs.

When FRP materials applied in civil engineering environments, generally, FRP materials are inevitably exposed to water or various solutions (such as alkaline, salt, etc.). Water uptake and diffusion in FRPs will bring in plasticization,

swelling, hydrolysis of polymer matrix, debonding of fibers from the resin, as well as the corrosion of fibers for glass or Aramid fibers [1, 2]. As a result, the mechanical properties tend to deteriorate with increasing the exposure time.

The property degradation of a GFRP composite in water or moist environments can be attributed to the effect of water ingress. During ageing, the resin matrix may undergo plasticization and hydrolysis. The plasticization effect, may leading to reduced glass transition temperatures and mechanical properties, is reversible. The hydrolysis effect will bring in permanent degradation of the resin system. The presence of fibers was reported to enhance those above effects [3]. This is attributed to the enhancement of water absorption with the degraded fiber-matrix interfaces, which will bring in an capillary effect.

In addition, debonding and cracks in the GFRP composites were also reported during ageing. Silane coupling agents showed effective in keeping the interfacial shear strength between fiber and matrix from permanent damage during immersion in water [4].

Besides, when subjected to sustained forces, FRP-structures will exhibit creep behavior due to the viscoelastic performances. The creep behavior of a FRP structure is dependent on the temperatures and the external forces. Creep of a FRP material may lead to “static fatigue” [2]. The creep behavior is essential to determine the long term loading capacity of a FRP structure.

In the present paper, a GFRP pipe was studied on the durability when subjected to immersion and sustained forces. The study is expected to understand the degradation mechanisms under such harsh conditions.

2 Experimental

2.1 GFRP Composite Samples

The testing samples were cut from GFRP square pipes, which were manufactured with a pultrusion process and supplied by Fukui Fibertech Co., Ltd, Toyohashi, Japan. The dimensions of the pipe are given in Fig. 1.

Samples for water immersion and three-point bending test were cut directly from the wall of the pipe. The dimensions of the samples for water immersion are 25 mm x 25 mm x 4.25 mm. The samples for three-point bending are 136 mm in length, 13mm in width and 4.25 mm in thickness.

2.2 Hygrothermal Ageing

The GFRP sample coupons for water sorption tests were schematically shown in Figure 2. The GFRP samples were soaked in distilled water baths at 20, 40 and 60°C, respectively.

The water uptake in the samples was detected by periodically recording the mass change of the samples. Samples were taken out of the baths and swiped off the surface water using tissue paper. An electronic balance with an accuracy of 0.01 mg was used to weigh the specimens. The presented data are an average of ten coupons. The water uptake of the sample was calculated with the following equation:

$$M_a = \frac{W_w - W_0}{W_0}$$

where M_a is the water uptake ratio, W_w is the mass of the samples after immersion in water, and W_0 is the initial mass of the samples (i.e., mass of the sample before ageing).

2.3 Flexural test

Flexural properties of the GFRP coupons were tested according to ASTM D 7264/D 7264M-07 (Flexural Properties of Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites) in three-point bending mode. The samples were cut into 160 x 13 x 4.25 mm³. The testing speed was set as 5 mm / min. For each condition, five samples were repeated and the average results were reported.

2.4 Short Beam Shear Strength test

The short beam shear strength (SBS) of the samples was tested according to ASTM D

2344/2344-00(M) (Standard Test Method for Short-Beam Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials and Their Laminates).

Samples

Samples for SBS test were cut from the pipe into 25mm in length, 8.5 mm in width and 4.25 mm in thickness. The testing speed was set as 2 mm/min. For each condition, five samples were repeated and the average results were reported.

2.5 Creep Behavior Testing

The creep test was conducted with the GFRP pipe, which were exposed to outdoor environments in Harbin, China.

A setup were designed and constructed for creep testing of the pipe in three-point bending mode. Figure 3 shows the loading status of the pipe. FBG (fiber Brag Grating) sensors were used to track the strain of the pipe during testing. The locations of the FBG sensors are schematically shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4 presents the photograph of the creep testing setup. The sustained loading is coming from dead weights. The yellow wires is connected to the FBG sensors.

The sustained bending forces are 40, 50 and 60 percent of the ultimate flexural strength of the pipe.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Water absorption and diffusion in GFRP

Fig. 5 presents the water uptake curves of the GFRP coupons during water immersion for 6 months. As shown, with increasing immersion temperatures, the more water was absorbed by the samples. In spite of this, the difference of the water uptake content due to the immersion temperatures is limited. The maximum water uptake content with temperature increase is 2.06%, 2.10% and 2.20%, respectively.

It is worth noting that no weight loss is observed for the current studied GFRP composites, which is frequently reported for GFRP composites especially at high immersion temperatures [5]. The mass loss is a direct indicator for hydrolysis of the composite. In addition to this, the surface of the aged samples after 6 month immersion at various temperatures does not show any changes, indicating no decomposition of the GFRP composites occurred.

To determine the coefficient of diffusion of water in the GFRP coupons, the classic Fick's law was used:

$$M_t = M_\infty \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[-7.3 \left(\frac{D_a t}{h^2} \right)^{0.75} \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

where M_t is the water uptake at time t , M_∞ is the quasi-equilibrium water uptake, D_a is the apparent coefficient of diffusion, and h is the thickness of the specimen (4.25mm).

With curve fitting, D_a and M_∞ are determined and given in Table 1. Clearly, the determined quasi-equilibrium water uptake is very close to the maximum water uptake as mentioned above. The temperature has negligible effect on it. As known, the equilibrium water uptake is related to the pore properties of the resin system. For most of the polymer systems, such as epoxy, vinyl ester, the temperature was reported not to affect M_∞ , generally [2].

It is of interest to note that the immersion temperatures also show low influence on D_a . With Arrhenius equation (see Equation 2), the activation energy (E_a) of the water diffusion is calculated.

$$D_a = D_o \exp(-E_a/RT) \quad (2)$$

where D_o is diffusion constant, R the universal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin. The calculated E_a is only 8.4 kJ/mol, which is much lower than reported values in a range of 30~80 kJ/mol. The much low E_a may be due to the water absorption mechanisms. For example, if the water is absorbed mainly by the void, defects, and the interfaces rather than by the resin matrix, the diffusion process will not be activated thermally, and the effect of temperature will be low. Thus, E_a is reduced remarkably.

3.2 Flexural properties

Figure 6 presents typical strain ~ stress curves of control samples, and aged samples after 6-month immersion in water at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60°C, respectively.

As shown, after immersion in water for 6 months, flexural strength and modulus of aged samples are all degraded. The higher the temperatures, the more degradation is found.

Figure 7 presents SEM pictures of water immersed samples at 20°C and 60°C for 6 months, respectively. As shown, there are still lots of resin attached on the

fiber surfaces in the case of the low temperature immersion. However, at higher temperature, very few resin attached on the surface of the fibers. This indicates the water immersion lead to weakening of the interfaces. The weakening of the interfaces is expected to be the main reason for the reduction of the flexural properties of the GFRP samples.

The influence of the immersion time on the flexural strength and modulus are summarized in Figure 8. It can be found that an increase in both the flexural strength and modulus was found after the initial 7-day immersion. Further increasing of the immersion time, however, both the flexural strength and modulus decrease steadily (Figure 8).

The initial increase of the mechanical properties has been reported for various FRP systems [6]. Post-curing effect and/or relaxation of the internal stress formed during pultrusion are believed to be responsible for the increase of the flexural properties. The retention of the flexural strength is 63%, 63% and 57% after 6 months immersion as the temperatures increasing from 20°C to 60°C. By contrast, the flexural modulus is relatively less deteriorated with the immersion time. The corresponding retention of the modulus is 89%, 84% and 81% with the increase of the immersion temperatures after 6 months immersion.

As regards to the influence of immersion temperatures, similar to the water uptake, both the flexural strength and modulus are less affected by the temperatures.

3.3 Short beam shear strength

Figure 9 shows variation of the short beam shear strength of GFRP samples immersed in water at various temperatures as a function of immersion time. After 6 months immersion, the retention of the short beam shear strength is 46%, 40% and 37% at 20°C, 40°C and 60°C, respectively. Clearly, the degradation of the short beam shear strength is much serious than that of the flexural strength (Figure 8b).

As known, short beam shear strength is more related to the interfacial shear strength of the FPR composites. The dramatic decrease of the short beam shear strength indicates that the water immersion brings in the damage of the interfaces between fiber and the resin matrix.

As mentioned in section of 3.1, the absorbed water may mainly exist in the void or the interface between fiber and resin matrix. Besides, as shown in

Figure 7, the degradation of the interface of aged samples especially at high temperatures is remarkable. Therefore, it is interesting to check the relationship between the water uptake content and the short beam shear strength.

Figure 10 presents the correlation between the short beam shear strength and the water uptake content. It can be found, as expected above, with the increase of the water uptake content, the short beam shear strength decreases steadily. This result further confirms that the water ingress in the composites deteriorates the interface shear strength.

It is also worth noting that the short beam shear strength of GFRP samples decreases almost linearly if the initial point is not considered.

In addition, with the similar water content, the higher the immersion temperatures, the more degradation of the short beam shear strength is observed (Figure 10). This indicates that the weakening of the interface is also dependent on the immersion temperatures. High temperatures accelerate the weakening of the interface.

3.4 Creep Behavior of GFRP Pipe

The pipes have been exposed to the outdoor environments of Harbin, China under sustained bending forces. The creep strain was measured with FBG sensors. Under 50% of flexural strength, the flexural strain reaches the equilibrium status in several hours, while under 30% of flexural strength it will take about 25 days.

4 Conclusions

A GFRP composite pipe was studied on water uptake, flexural properties and creep behaviors. When subjected to water immersion, the GFRP specimens absorbed about 2 wt.% of water content. It was found that the saturation water content and the coefficient of diffusion are negligibly affected by the immersion temperatures. This is because the diffusion of the water in the present GFRP composites may be mainly occurred along the interfaces between the fiber and resin matrix, rather than through the resin matrix. This is also confirmed by the activation energy of the diffusion, which is only 8 kJ/mol, much lower than those of polymer resins or polymer based composites.

Water immersion leads to the degradation of the flexural properties due to the damage of the

interfaces. Meanwhile, the flexural strength is more sensitive to the water immersion than the modulus. The short beam shear strength is reduced by the water immersion dramatically, which is correlated to the water uptake content. The higher the water uptake content, the more reduced the short beam shear strength. The creep resistance of the pipe was investigated.

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References

- [1] Xian, G. J. and Karbhari, V. M., *Segmental relaxation of water-aged ambient cured epoxy*. Polymer Degradation and Stability, Vol. **92**, pp 1650-1659, 2007.
- [2] Xian, G. J. and Karbhari, V.M., *DMTA based investigation of hygrothermal ageing of an epoxy system used in rehabilitation*. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, Vol. 104, No. 2, pp 1084-1094, 2007.
- [3] Ghorbel I. and Valentin D., *Hygrothermal effects on the physic-chemical properties of pure and glass fiber reinforced polyester and vinylester resins*, Polymer Composites, Vol. 14, No. 4, pp 324-334, 1993.
- [4] Bian X. S., Ambrosio L., Kenny J. M., and Nicolais L., *Effect of water absorption on the behavior of E-Glass fiber / nylon 6 composites*, Polymer Composites, Vol. 12, No. 5, 1991.
- [5] Nishizaki I. and Meiarashi S., *Long term deterioration of GFRP in water and moist environment*, Journal of Composites for Construction, Vol. 6, pp21-27, 2002.
- [6] Xian G. J., Li H. and Su X. S., *Water absorption and hygrothermal ageing of ultraviolet cured glass-fiber reinforced acrylate composites*, Vol. 33, No. 7, Polymer Composites, pp1120-1128, 2012

Table 1 D_a and M_∞ determined with Equation 1 according to Fick's law.

Immersion Temperature (°C)	D_a ($\times 10^{-7} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$)	M_∞ (%)
20	8.53	2.01
40	10.06	2.02
60	12.92	2.05

Fig. 1. Dimensions of the GFRP pipes, $a=50\text{mm}$, $b=41.5\text{mm}$, $t=4.25\text{mm}$.

Fig. 3. GFRP pipe under flexural force.

Fig. 2. GFRP sample for water uptake test. Note, a is equal to 25mm , and t is equal to 4.25mm , which cut from the pipe.

Fig. 4. Creep testing setup for GFRP pipes in outdoor environments (Harbin, China)

Fig. 5. Water uptake curves of GFRP coupons at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60°C.

Fig. 6. Typical flexural strain ~ stress curves of GFRP coupons after 6 months immersion at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60°C.

a

b

Fig.7. SEM pictures of flexural fracture surfaces of water immersed GFRP samples at 20°C (a) and 60°C (b).

a

b

Fig 8 .Variation of flexural modulus (a) and flexural strength (b) as a function of immersion time. Note, W20 means immersion in water at 20°C, the remaining consistent.

Fig.9.Variation of the short beam shear strength as a function of immersion time. Note, W20 means immersion in water at 20°C, the remaining consistent.

Fig. 10. Variation of short beam shear strength of GFRP samples immersed in water at 20°C, 40°C and 60°C as a function of water content.

Fig.11. Creep strain of GFRP pipes under various sustained flexural forces in outdoor environment, Harbin, China.